

Review Article

Prevalence of Neck Pain among Computer User-A Systematic Review

Sharick Shamsi¹, Shabana Khan², Nourah Ali Al Muhanna³, Abdullah S. Bin Hussein⁴, Abdulmohsen Hasan Abdullah Al Ghamdi⁵, Zafrul Hasan⁶, Ali Akhtar⁷, Saleh Mohammed Alamri⁸

¹Senior Physiotherapist at Raj Nursing Home, Gorakhpur, India

²Physiotherapist at Prince Sultan Military Medical City, Riyadh, KSA

³Chief Physiotherapist at Prince Sultan Military Medical City, Riyadh, KSA

⁴Senior Physiotherapist at Prince Sultan Military Medical City, Riyadh, KSA

⁵Chief of Physical Therapy Department at Sharurah Armed Forced Hospital, KSA

⁶Researcher, College of Nursing, King Saud University, Riyadh, KSA

⁷Researcher IT and Quality Unit, College of Pharmacy, King Saud University, Riyadh, KSA

⁸Assistant Director of Pharmacy for Material Management, Department of Pharmaceutical Services at PSMCC, Riyadh, KSA

Corresponding Author Email: sharickshamsi@gmail.com

Received: August 02, 2022

Accepted: August 31, 2022

Published: September 15, 2022

Abstract: Background: Complaints of arm, neck, and shoulders (CANS) is a common problem among patients whose work involves computer use, but often ignored most importantly by the physicians partly due to not being able to appreciate the importance of taking a careful detailed occupational history of exposure to a repetitive activity involving upper arms. **Method:** This systematic review includes cross-sectional study and observational study. Searching done by Google Scholar, PubMed and PEDro from 2013 to 2019. We used terms like-Neck pain, computer, work, information technology, professionals, pain, health problems, discomfort, musculoskeletal diseases, musculo-skeletal system and physiotherapy management. **Result:** Present outcomes show the prevalence of neck pain in computer user's females has high prevalence than males. The search resulted in 100 articles but only 07 articles were selected for the study based on criteria. **Conclusion:** Present review shows that prevalence of neck pain is higher in females when compared to males.

Keywords: Neck Pain, Computer user, health problem, information technology.

Introduction

With the passage of time, there is advancement in technology. Due to this advancement in technology, our method of working has modernized. Like after the invention of computers, there is so much transformation in our working technique. It is used a lot in our office setups. Although it plays an essential role in our lives but it has some disadvantages. Continuous work on computer results in excessive tension on muscles of body especially musculature of neck which causes pain in the neck region¹. The neck pain is a common cause of disability and health problem in the general population. Neck pain is one of the common musculoskeletal problems. Neck Pain can be caused by the stress over the musculoskeletal system due to postural disorders and may also be associated with other causes such as intervertebral disc herniation, nerve compression, or fracture. Prevalence of Neck pain is reported to range from 43% to 66.7%, which increases along with aging. Study conducted by March et al. on individuals over 65 years of age, the prevalence of NP was found to be 38.7%².

The overall usage of computers is firmly related to expanded prevalence in neck and shoulder discomfort. The lifetime prevalence of neck pain is reported as high as 80%³. One of the causes of neck pain is whiplash injury, in which there is sudden flexion and hyperextension of the head. Degenerative changes in the vertebrae are also responsible for neck pain like spinal osteoarthritis. It affects spinal intervertebral discs and facet joints. Bony spurs develop which pinch a spinal nerve root and thus it causes inflammation and pain in neck region. In some serious cases, patient does not have any symptoms of degeneration although these changes cause pain, problems relating to nerves and hardening of the neck and cervical spine⁴.

Several interventions have been proposed to rectify the postures of computer users through self-efficacy, including internet training⁵ and real-time visual feedback⁶.

Nevertheless, education regarding posture has its role in preventing adverse postures and movements⁷. Proper rest breaks, physical exercise, adequate sleep and relaxation at home are effective strategies to cope with the overall health problems among frequent computer users such as software professionals⁸.

Use of an external keyboard has shown to be beneficial in reducing the neck and shoulder pain^{9,10}. In environments where external devices are not available a 12° incline placed on a standard height desk may be the most desirable peripheral for portable computers for improving head and neck posture¹¹, whereas setting the monitor tilt angle at 130° in a notebook computer has shown to significantly reduce the neck and shoulder discomfort¹².

Thus, this review was conducted to determine the neck pain in computer user.

Methods

This review study is performed in accordance to PRISMA-Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta Analyses¹³.

Search Strategy

The searching was done in PubMed, Google Scholar and PEDro. Key words like-Neck pain, computer, work, information technology, professionals, pain, health problems, discomfort, musculoskeletal diseases, musculo-skeletal system and physiotherapy management. We included past 07 years articles published in English language only from 2013-2019.

The title and abstracts of all articles in the searches were screened in accordance with the inclusion and exclusion criteria to identify potentially eligible articles. Full texts of potential articles were read and assessed independently by the two reviewers.

Inclusions and exclusion criteria

We included cross sectional studies that are observational assessing neck pain in computer users. We excluded studies containing “computer user and neck pain” in the title but not being correct in terms, as those articles evaluated neck pain in other users.

Data Extraction

Data were extracted to and the following features were integrated into the database: number of participants, methods of inclusion, and the prevalence of neck pain categorized by severity.

Results

Studies identified

After implementing the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 100 articles were retrieved using the key words-Neck pain, computer, work, information technology, professionals, pain, health problems, discomfort, musculoskeletal diseases, musculo-skeletal system and physiotherapy management. 65

articles were excluded as they were found in more than one database. For eligibility criteria 35 articles were screened. Further 28 articles excluded because either they were not available in full text, objective not available, they did not meet exclusion and inclusion criteria or no control group (Figure-1). Finally, 07 articles were selected by agreement for quality assessment phase.

General data of the included studies

Selected articles in this review are summarized in **Table 1** including given parameters: author-year, study design, subjects, outcome measures, study region and results. In 07 included studies in this study 6 were cross sectional study^{14,15,16,17,18,20} one study is observational study¹⁹. All studies were conducted between 2013 and 2019. Number of participants in the studies ranged from 50 to 669.

Outcome Measures

The key result tests are Age, Gender, Duration of job, Daily hours of work, Physical exercise, Self-administrable questionnaire, Semi-structured questionnaire, Neck Disability Index, Maastricht Upper Extremity Questionnaire, Chi square.

Table 1. Description of the included studies

Author	Study design	Subject	Study region	Outcome measures	Result
Younis N, et al. ¹⁴	Cross sectional study	N=309	Punjab University Lahore, Govt. College University Lahore, Education University Lahore, and The Resource Group Lahore.	Self-administrable Questionnaire.	Female computer operators were more victims of neck pain as compared to male computer operators.
Bhalala SH. ¹⁵	Cross sectional study	N=100 M-81 F- 19	Enwisen Consulting LLP, Adajan, Surat, Pranesh Agrawal & Co. Chartered Accountants, Chhapania Sheri, Surat, Finlogic technologies India Pvt. Limited, Udhana, Surat.	Semi-structured questionnaire, Neck Disability Index.	From this study it is concluded that 55 % of the people of age group 20 to 50 years have mild and moderate neck pain.
Rasim Ul Hasanat M, et al. ¹⁶	Cross sectional study	N=185	Not Available	Self-administrable Questionnaire.	Intensive computer users are likely to experience at least one episode of computer-associated neck pain.
Mohan V, et al. ¹⁷	Cross sectional study	N=206	Two medium- sized software companies in Bangalore.	Maastricht Upper Extremity Questionnaire, Chi- square	Complaints of arm, neck, and shoulders (CANS) is highly prevalent among computer professionals working in small and medium- sized companies. Provision of adequate workspace and ergonomic designs of workstations are the modifiable risk factors which can be addressed by the employers to reduce the morbidity associated with CANS. Employees could correct postures and improve work habits.
Zain A, et al. ¹⁸	Cross sectional study	N=669	Computer operators from Lahore city.	Chi Square test	There was 42.90% prevalence of neck pain in computer operators of Lahore. It was also found that neck pain is associated with gender and smoking. According to this study, no significant association of neck pain was seen with working hours and family history of neck pain.
Sabeen F, et al. ¹⁹	Observational study	N=50	Office workers (computer users) and students.	Individual demographic characteristics, Work environment factors, Total duration of daily sitting at work, Frequency of breaks from sitting, postural	So duration of computer use and frequency of breaks are associated with neck pain at work. Severe Neck pain was found in people who use computer for more than 5 hours a day.

Khan ASK, Faizan M. ²⁰	Cross sectional study	N=50	NKP Salve Institute of Medical Sciences; Research Centre and Lata Mangeshkar Hospital, Nagpur (tertiary care and medical institute).	care. Age, Gender, Duration of job, Daily hours of work, Physical exercise.	The prevalence is more in females (60%). The neck pain increased with increase in age, 66% neck pain was found in people between 50-60 years. The prevalence of neck pain was low among those who do regular exercise, in our study only 30% of computer users do regular exercise out of which only 36% develop neck pain.
-----------------------------------	-----------------------	------	--	---	---

Discussions

Our review included the minimal quantity of participants which was 50, and the maximum was 669. We counted 1,569 participants. The based on the literature the prevalence of neck pain with a minimum prevalence of 36% and a maximum of 42.90%. One article found that 18% of People have mild neck pain and in young adults incidence of neck and shoulder pain is high¹⁵. Van Der Heuvel et al. concluded that sustained sporting activities have a favorable effect on neck/shoulder symptoms²¹.

Arie et al. found that workers who sat for more than 95% of the working time, the risk of neck pain was twice as high as for worker who hardly ever worked in a sitting position. From present study, we can say that people work more than 3 hour having 55% mild to moderate pain²². One of the study found that women had higher prevalence rates of upper extremity musculoskeletal complaints–region wise as well as overall, than men²³.

Another cross-sectional study was conducted in Ahmedabad by Shah and Patel in 2015. According to that study, there was 47% prevalence of neck pain¹. A cross sectional study was conducted by Janwantanakul et al. to find out the prevalence of musculoskeletal complaints in office workers. They reported that musculoskeletal issues relating to neck pain were 42%²⁴. A cross sectional study was conducted to know the 1 year incidence of neck pain in office workers. Data were collected from 512 individuals. Cagnie et al. found that office workers have prevalence rate of 45.5% for the neck pain²⁵. Another study was conducted by Diepenmaat et al. to find out the prevalence of neck pain in adults. He found that there is 11.5% prevalence of neck pain in adults²⁶.

Conclusion

This systematic review was conducted to investigate the prevalence of neck pain among computer user. While it is known that computer users have neck pain the cause is still an enigma. Future clinical research in this area should be prospective in design, evaluate effectiveness, efficacy, and cost effectiveness of primary preventive strategies for neck pain, and further explore the potential adverse effects of engaging in prolonged exposure to computer work at a young age.

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

1. Shah SA, Patel PR. Prevalence of neck pain in computer operators. *NHL J Med Sci.* 2015;4(1):5-11.
2. March LM, Brnabic AJ, Skinner JC, Schwarz JM, Finnegan T, Druce J, Brooks PM. Musculoskeletal disability among elderly people in the community. *Med J Australia.* 1998;168(9):439-42.
3. Breen PP, Nisar A, ÓLaighin G. Evaluation of a single accelerometer based biofeedback system for real-time correction of neck posture in computer users. In *Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society, 2009. Annual International Conference of the IEEE 2009*;7269-7272.

4. Al Shehri A, Khan S, Shamsi S, Almureef SS. Comparative study of mulligan (SNAGS) and Maitland mobilization in neck pain. *Europ J Phys Edu Sport Sci.* 2018; 5(1):19-29.
5. Keykhaie Z, Zareban I, Shahrakipoor M, Hormozi M, Sharifi-Rad J, Masoudi G, Rahimi F. Implementation of internet training on posture reform of computer users in Iran. *Acta Inform Med.* 2014;22(6):379-84.
6. Duffy P, Smeaton AF. Measuring the Effectiveness of User Interventions in Improving the Seated Posture of Computer Users. Michael JOG, Hamed, Vahdat-Nejadeds. *Evolving Ambient Intelligence. AmI 2013. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 413.* Springer, Cham.
7. Speklé EM, Hoozemans MJ, Blatter BM, Heinrich J, van der Beek AJ, Knol DL, Bongers PM, van Dieën JH. Effectiveness of a questionnaire based intervention programme on the prevalence of arm, shoulder and neck symptoms, risk factors and sick leave in computer workers: a cluster randomised controlled trial in an occupational setting. *BMC Musculoskelet Disord.* 2010;11: 99-110.
8. Das R. Occupational health concerns of software professionals and their coping strategies. *Int J Manage Res Bus Strat.* 2012;1(1):81-6.
9. Malińska M, Bugajska J. The influence of occupational and non-occupational factors on the prevalence of musculoskeletal complaints in users of portable computers. *Int J Occup Safety Ergo.* 2010;16(3):337-43.
10. Jacobs K, Kaldenberg J, Markowitz J, Wuest E, Hellman M, Umez-Eronini A, Arsenault M, Walker B, Hall V, Ciccarelli M, Parsons R. An ergonomics training program for student notebook computer users: Preliminary outcomes of a six-year cohort study. *Work.* 2013;44(2):221-30.
11. Asundi K, Odell D, Luce A, Dennerlein JT. Changes in posture through the use of simple inclines with notebook computers placed on a standard desk. *Appl Ergo.* 2012;43(2):400-7.
12. Chiou WK, Chou WY, Chen BH. Notebook computer use with different monitor tilt angle: effects on posture, muscle activity and discomfort of neck pain users. *Work.* 2012;41(Supplement 1):2591-5.
13. Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG, PRISMA Group, Reprint-Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. *Phy Ther.* 2009;89(9):873–880.
14. Younis N, Afzal MW, Ahmad A, Ghafoor I, Waqas MS. Prevalence of work related neck pain in computer operators. *Rawal Med J.* 2017;42(3):344-6.
15. Bhalala SH. Prevalence of Neck Pain in Computer Workers in Surat City: A Cross-sectional Study. *Int J Curr Res Rev.* 2019;11(20):1-8.
16. Rasim Ul Hasanat M, Ali SS, Rasheed A, Khan M. Frequency and associated risk factors for neck pain among software engineers in Karachi, Pakistan. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2017;67(7):1009-1012.
17. Mohan V, Inbaraj LR, George CE, Norman G. Prevalence of complaints of arm, neck, and shoulders among computer professionals in Bangalore: A cross-sectional study. *J Fam Med Prim Care.* 2019;8(1):171-77.
18. Zain A, Ahmed A, Hanif K. Prevalence of Neck Pain in Computer Operators of Lahore City. *Asian J Allied Health Sci.* 2017;2(4):14-18.
19. Sabeen F, Bashir MS, Hussain SI, Ehsan S. Prevalance of neck pain in computer users. *Ann King Edward Med Univ.* 2013;19(2):137-43.

20. Khan ASK, Faizan M. Neck-pain in computer-users. *Panacea J Med Sci.* 2016;6(2):88-91.
21. van den Heuvel SG, Heinrich J, Jans MP, Van der Beek AJ, Bongers PM. The effect of physical activity in leisure time on neck and upper limb symptoms. *Prevent Med.* 2005;41(1):260-7.
22. Ariens GAM, Bongers PM, Hoogendoorn WE, Van Der Wal G, Van Mechelen W. High physical and psychosocial load at work and sickness absence due to neck pain. *Scand J Work Environ Health.* 2002;28(4):222-31.
23. Bekiari EI, Lyrakos GN, Damigos D, Mavreas V, Chanopoulos K, Dimoliatis ID. A validation study and psychometrical evaluation of the Maastricht Upper Extremity Questionnaire (MUEQ) for the Greek-speaking population. *J Musculoskelet Neuronal Interact.* 2011;11(1):52-76.
24. Janwantanakul P, Pensri P, Jiamjarasrangsi V, Sinsongsook T. Prevalence of self-reported musculoskeletal symptoms among office workers. *Occupat Med.* 2008;58(6):436-8.
25. Cagnie B, Danneels L, Van Tiggelen D, De Loose V, Cambier D. Individual and work related risk factors for neck pain among office workers: a cross sectional study. *Europ Spine J.* 2007;16(5):679-86.
26. Diepenmaat AC, Van der Wal MF, De Vet HC, Hirasing RA. Neck/shoulder, low back, and arm pain in relation to computer use, physical activity, stress, and depression among Dutch adolescents. *Pediatrics.* 2006;117(2):412-6.

Citation: Shamsi S, Khan S, Al Muhanna NA, Hussein ASB, Al Ghamdi AHA, Hasan Z, Akhtar A, Alamri SM. Prevalence of Neck Pain among Computer User-A Systematic Review. *Int J Rec Innov Med Clin Res.* 2022;4(3):99-105.

Copyright: ©2022 Shamsi S, et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.